

Effect of solvent on protonation equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid

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Protonation equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid are investigated in 0–60% (v/v) aquo-acetonitrile media at an ionic strength of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} and temperature 303 K. The best fit chemical models are arrived at using MINQUAD75 based on statistical parameters. The change in protonation constants with the dielectric constant of the medium is attributed to the electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces.

L-Glutamine is found on the outer surface of globular proteins. It is used in the brain for the respiration and for the biosynthesis of γ -aminobutyric acid, a neurotransmitter. It is also used for growth and differentiation of neural cells¹.

Succinic acid is involved in citric acid and glyoxalate cycles. Many bacteria and plants convert two-carbon acetyl units into four-carbon succinate units for energy production and biosynthesis in the glyoxalate cycle. Succinate is released in the biosynthesis of collagen from the proline residue and α -ketoglutarate.

Acetonitrile (AN) is a protophobic dipolar aprotic solvent and does not form hydrogen bonds with solute². IR studies show that the protophobic character of AN is due to the formation of dimers³. Trouton constant indicates⁴ the less ordered bulk structure of AN compared to that of water. AN acts as structure-breaker of water due to the formation of water-AN molecular species. The hydrogen-bonded water-AN species⁵ increases the basicity of hydroxyl hydrogen of water due to the presence of lone-pair of electrons on nitrogen atom of AN. Thus, in the presence of AN the water structure breaks down resulting in more basic monomeric water molecules and increased solvation of H^+ . Hence, the protonation equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid are studied in the presence of acetonitrile to understand the influence of cosolvent on the speciation.

Results and Discussion

Alkalimetric titration and formation curves in water-AN mixtures reveal that the acido-basic equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid are of significance in the pH range 2.0–10.0 and 2.0–7.0, respectively. In the modeling strategy the dimeric forms of these acids L_2H_x are not considered as there is no observed drift in the formation curves for different initial concentrations of these acids. The results of the best-fit models obtained using the computer program

MINQUAD75⁶ along with some important statistical parameters are given in Table 1.

A very low standard deviation in $\log \beta$ values indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ligand and hydrogen ion at all experimental points, corrected for degrees of freedom) indicate that the experimental data can be represented by the model. Small values of arithmetic mean, standard deviation, mean deviation and variance for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of kurtosis and skewness should be three and zero, respectively. The kurtosis values in the present studies indicate that the residuals of many systems form leptokurtic and a few form platykurtic pattern. The values of skewness between -0.37 and -2.09 evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence least squares method can be applied to the present data.

The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic R value. These statistical parameters, thus, show that the best-fit models portray the acido-basic equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid in water-AN mixtures. The coincidence of simulated and experimental primary data curves supports the validity of the model. The protonation constants of L-glutamine and succinic acid reported in the literature are given in Table 2 along with the experimental conditions and computational methods. The protonation constants in the present study are in agreement with the literature values.

Effect of systematic errors :

MINQUAD75 has no in-built provision to study the effect of systematic errors in the concentration of ingredients on the magnitude of protonation constants. To rely upon the best-fit chemical model for critical evaluation and compila-

Table 1. Best-fit chemical models of acido-basic equilibria in water-acetonitrile mixtures

Ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. = 303 K								
AN % (v/v)	log β_1 (SD)	log β_2 (SD)	NP	U_{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2	R
L-Glutamine (pH range : 1.5–11.0)								
00	9.27 (1)	11.66(2)	147	0.59	-0.43	3.84	31.77	0.016
10	9.60 (1)	11.99(1)	103	7.80	-1.41	5.98	13.42	0.010
20	9.57 (1)	12.05(1)	94	9.44	-1.64	7.08	13.36	0.012
30	9.61 (1)	12.18(2)	108	12.41	-1.04	3.44	11.26	0.013
40	9.69 (2)	12.53(4)	110	40.56	-1.09	3.62	14.91	0.022
50	9.76 (1)	12.94(2)	112	11.60	-0.84	4.97	42.21	0.011
60	9.87 (1)	13.58(3)	112	17.11	-0.94	4.82	29.14	0.014
Succinic acid (pH range : 3.0–7.0)								
00	5.43 (1)	9.46(1)	88	0.21	-1.31	6.82	10.36	0.014
10	5.76 (8)	10.09(1)	60	4.02	-2.09	9.75	32.40	0.010
20	5.89 (2)	10.40(2)	62	0.40	-0.99	5.07	7.48	0.003
30	6.21 (5)	10.98(4)	59	0.69	-1.01	6.11	8.10	0.004
40	6.33 (5)	11.28(7)	60	1.73	-0.80	3.85	1.87	0.006
50	6.57 (3)	11.79(4)	56	0.81	-0.57	3.16	0.43	0.004
60	6.85 (3)	12.38(4)	51	0.56	-0.37	3.08	1.69	0.003

$U_{\text{corr}} = U/(NP-m) \times 10^8$, where m = number of species.

Table 2. Protonation constants of L-glutamine and succinic acid reported in literature

Sl. no.	log β		Temp. K	Ionic strength	Computer program used	Instrumental method	Ref
	011	012					
L-Glutamine							
1.	9.01	11.18	298	0.1	-	-	7
2.	9.64	12.36	298	3.0	-	-	7
3.	8.94	11.08	298	0.5	-	-	7
4.	8.70	10.89	310	0.15	-	-	7
5.	8.97	11.36	-	-	-	-	8
6.	8.70	11.24	303	0.1	MINIQUAD	pH-metry	9
Succinic acid							
1.	5.32	9.35	298	0.15	Graphical	Potentiometry	10
2.	5.30	9.39	298	0.46	Graphical	Potentiometry	10
3.	5.67	9.85	298	0.0	Graphical	Potentiometry	10
4.	5.08	8.98	298	0.5	MINIQUAD	Potentiometry	11
5.	5.20	9.18	298	1.0	-	Potentiometry	12
6.	5.24	-	298	0.1	-	-	13
7.	5.31	-	298	0.1	-	-	13
8.	5.09	-	298	0.5	-	-	13
9.	5.11	-	298	1.0	-	-	13
10.	5.30	9.30	303	0.1	MINIQUAD	pH-metry	14

tion, pessimistic errors are introduced in the influential factors like concentrations of mineral acid, ligand and alkali. This investigation is useful because the data acquisition is

done under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies. Results of typical systems are given in Table 3. The order of influence of errors in the ingredients on the

Table 3. Effect of errors in influential factors on the protonation constants of succinic acid in 20% (v/v) water-AN mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β (SD)	
		011	012
log <i>F</i> *	0	5.89 (2)	10.40 (2)
	-5	5.89 (2)	10.39 (2)
	-2	5.89 (2)	10.40 (2)
	+2	5.89 (2)	10.40 (2)
	+5	5.90 (2)	10.41 (2)
Alkali	-5	6.15 (14)	10.77 (18)
	-2	5.99 (7)	10.54 (9)
	+2	5.80 (4)	10.27 (5)
	+5	5.66 (13)	10.08 (18)
Acid	-5	5.89 (1)	10.39 (2)
	-2	5.89 (2)	10.40 (2)
	+2	5.90 (2)	10.41 (3)
	+5	5.90 (2)	10.42 (3)
Ligand	-5	5.86 (2)	10.36 (4)
	-2	5.88 (2)	10.38 (2)
	+2	5.91 (2)	10.42 (4)
	+5	5.93 (3)	10.44 (5)

*Correction factor, log *F* = pH_{cal} - pH_{expt}

magnitudes of protonation constants is alkali > ligand > acid > log *F*.

Effect of dielectric constant :

Co-solvent influences the equilibria in solution due to change in the dielectric constant of the medium. The change in dielectric constant varies the relative contribution of electrostatic and non-electrostatic interactions which in turn vary the magnitudes of protonation constants. If the electrostatic forces alone operate, the logarithm of protonation constant should vary linearly as a function of reciprocal of the dielectric constant of the medium. The linear plots in water-AN mixtures reveal that this is true. The small non-linearity in L-glutamine may be due to the contributions from non-electrostatic forces which resulted out of the existence of zwitterionic form of the ligand.

In water-urea mixtures, as reported in the literature¹⁵, there was a decrease in log *K*¹¹ values for both L-glutamine and succinic acid. The log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ values of L-glutamine decreased from 8.74 (5.80%, w/w) to 7.76 (36.83%, w/w) and 2.07 to 1.53, respectively. Those of succinic acid decreased from 5.04 (5.80%, w/w) to 4.25 (36.83%, w/w) and 3.72 to 3.09, respectively. The reason for this trend is two-fold. Urea forms zwitterion which changes the dielectric constant of the medium. And urea also acts as a ligand and competes with the ligand for protons¹⁶. Hence, the protonation constants of the ligands decreased in the presence of urea.

Distribution diagrams :

L-Glutamine has three functional groups (amino, carboxyl and amido) but only amino and carboxyl groups participate in protonation equilibria. Succinic acid has two carboxyl groups and both are protonated. Typical distribution plots given in Fig. 1 show the existence of LH₂⁺, LH and L⁻ for L-glutamine and LH₂, LH⁻ and L²⁻ for succinic acid. The zwitterionic form (LH) of L-glutamine is present to an extent of 90% in the pH range 3.0–8.0. The concentrations of LH₂ and LH⁻ forms of succinic acid remain same

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagrams of (A) L-glutamine and (B) succinic acid in 20% water-AN mixture, along with formation curves.

Fig. 2. Protonation equilibria of L-glutamine and succinic acid

with increased AN content but the maximum concentration of LH^- is shifted to higher pH. These two observations indicate the stabilization of the two species with increased concentration of AN. The protonation equilibria and the pH ranges of existence of the species are shown in Fig. 2.

Experimental

L-Glutamine and succinic acid were of G.R. grade (E. Merck). The errors crept into the determination of the concentrations were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification (ANOVA). Strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method¹⁷.

The titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations (10–60%, v/v) of acetonitrile in water, maintaining an ionic strength of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} with NaCl at $303.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ K}$. The amount of L-glutamine or succinic acid in different experiments was in the range 0.45–0.75 mmol. A Systronic 335 pH meter was used. The glass electrode was equilibrated in water-AN mixture and the calomel electrode was filled with water-AN mixture of equivalent composition as that of titrand. Titrations were carried out with 0.4 mol dm^{-3} NaOH solution.

The approximate protonation constants of L-glutamine and succinic acid were calculated with the computer program SCPHD¹⁸. The protonation constants were refined and the best-fit chemical models were arrived at using the computer program MINIQAD75.

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